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Research Article

**THE REHABILITATION AFTER CRITICAL ILLNESS IN THE
PEOPLE HAVING INFECTION DUE TO COVID-19**¹Dr Hafiza Aqsa Faiz, ¹Dr. Maryam Khan, ²Dr Mubashara Khan¹Dera Ghazi Khan Medical College²Govt Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital Sialkot**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To determine the rehabilitation service after the illness due to COVID-19 as COVID-19 has been proved as pandemic outbreak in all over the world. People who have affected due to COVID-19 are highly affected due to respiratory distress syndrome and the special management by rehabilitation center is required for the cure of disease.

Technique: The cross-sectional analytical study was conducted by use of almost 300 patients who were diagnosed with COVID-19 positive in Multan. The questionnaire was prepared by online methods and was distributed among affected people present in the hospitals. The questionnaire was filled by the patients and for the patients who were unable to fill the questionnaire was presented to their relatives or other healthcare. Chi test was conducted to find the accuracy of the results.

Results: The result has showed that various symptoms have been showed due to COVID-19 due to which the services of rehabilitation centers were required. The most common and severe symptom related to the disease is respiratory acute disorders. 67.6% patients have experienced the symptom of cough due to the disease. Fever is also an important indication due to which rehabilitation services are required. 87.9% cases have dealt with fever in the disease.

Conclusion: The pandemic situation of corona has affected all the sectors present in all over the world including developed and developing countries. The rehabilitation services have also being infection in Multan due to availability of such services on small scale.

Keywords: COVID-19, Rehabilitation services, pandemic situation, Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome

Corresponding author:**Dr. Hafiza Aqsa Faiz,**

Dera Ghazi Khan Medical College

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

The pandemic of corona virus is affecting many sectors in all over the world including rehabilitation services (1). The owners of the rehabilitation services claimed that it is a threat for major rehabilitation centers and leading to the failure of all kind of centers no matter on small sector or large sector. The situation is being worse from day to day due to which more rehabilitation center are needed because less rehabilitation centers are present in Multan (2). Most of the countries such as Pakistan do not have appropriate and authentic diagnostic and hospital facilities for identification, isolation and treatment of the patients during this pandemic and these also not able to trade diagnostic kits from other countries (3). Various symptoms are present in the patients due to COVID-19 from which fever, cough, fatigue and sputum production are most common (4). All the symptoms needs rehabilitation centers for cure but the number of rehabilitation centers are less in the country especially in small cities such as Multan. The already present rehabilitation centers are not enough to meet the challenge due to which they are also being affected (5).

METHODOLOGY:

The cross-sectional observational study was conducted to find the situation in the rehabilitation centers of Multan, Pakistan. Total numbers of 300 patients were selected to determine the situation. The experience of the patients during the disease in rehabilitation centers was determined by patients or

their relatives by filling questionnaires. The time selected for the study was 3 months as ranges from March 2020 to May 2020. Almost 20 questions were selected for the study by the patients. The patients were getting healthcare facilities from the rehabilitation of Multan, therefore, the information about rehabilitation and their symptoms were asked by those patients. The sample was sufficient for the study because average can be determined by getting information from small sample of any region. The questionnaire was approved by Healthcare authority of Pakistan to prevent any official problem related to the study. The study has been conducted online due to lockdown and quarantine situation. The inclusion criteria for the study were the patients who were admitted in the rehabilitation center of Multan, or have ever been admitted in those centers due to COVID-19 positive situation. The people above age 20 were selected for the study to collect the real based data. The patients who have experienced the rehabilitation center prior pandemic situation of COVID-19 were excluded from the study. Furthermore, the patients below the age of 20 or with any other disease such as pre-eclampsia, chronic hypertension, diabetes mellitus, HIV infection, antepartum haemorrhage and mental illness were excluded from the study. Chi chart technique was used to analyze the results obtained from the study to determine the real situation of rehabilitations services present in Multan.

RESULTS:

No	Symptoms	Percentage
1	Fever	87.9
2	Dry Cough	67.7
3	Fatigue	38.1
4	Sputum production	33.4
5	Shortness of breath	18.6
6	Joint Pain	14.8
7	Sore Throat	13.9
8	Headache	13.6
9	Chills	11.4
10	Nausea	5
11	Nasal Congestion	4.8
12	Diarrhoea	3.7

The result has showed that most of the patients have experienced fever during the condition of COVID-19. 87.9% were the patients who have filled the questionnaire and have admitted in the hospitals has experienced fever. 67.7% patients were having dry cough, 38.1% have fatigue, 33.4% were having sputum production, 18.6% were dealing with shortness of breath. Furthermore, it has been found that 14.8% of the patients were having muscle pain, 13.9% were having sore throat, 13.6% had experienced headache. Only 3.7% of the patients were having diarrhea during the situation of COVID-19.

DISCUSSION:

COVID-19 is proving itself a most serious and dangerous disease that is not only leading to the disease and death of people but also increasing the financial issue because countries have made lockdowns and restricted the movement of people from one place to another. All kinds of functions have been restricted due to disease and get-together of any type is now banned for handling the situation. This outbreak has affected all the fields including business, industries, tourism and hospitality. The restriction of moving has affected the tourism and industries because the people cannot go for work because transport is close. The owners of business sectors are claiming that this situation has affected their business very badly (6).

The pandemic is affecting both personal and professional lives of people and leads to development of various other problems and disease due to stress and depression of disease. The routine of people has been destroyed due to lockdown and unemployment is increasing day by day in all over the world. The big shares of market have been altered and shares of companies are sold and bought that is thus affecting the individual saving account and value of pensions. FTSE, one of the top most organization has lost its growth sale by -24.5% that is a great fall of company and cannot be

covered for long time (7). According to a electronic research, it has been found that more than 30 million people only in US have lost their job in last few months due to COVID-19. The month of April and May is proving as the most difficult time of all people due to increase rate of unemployment and decrease productivity (8).

Business is highly affected by the health, political and economic security risk as in this pandemic situation the business of all the countries have reduces at a high level and can cause the risks of economy of the countries. In this pandemic it also affects the tech industry shipments at a high level. Corona virus is not an exception because any disease can be pandemic and affect the business at global level. It is a challenge for the government to take steps to overcome the pandemic situation so that business runs as before this pandemic situation (9). This pandemic situation cause most affect on the supply chain industries. There is a need to take steps so that business can run in an authentic way such as make sops and restrict all the employees to follow them because if these steps cannot be taken the hundreds of employees that are engaged in a business are unemployed and have no other source of income so poverty rate also increased and it may also cause death of the people due to shortage of food (10).

CONCLUSION:

It has been concluded from the study the pandemic situation of COVID-19 has not only affected business and economic sector but also negatively affects the rehabilitation centers due to unavailability of the enough sources especially in developing countries such as Pakistan. The study has been conducted in Multan to determine the situation and it has been found that the most known symptoms with COVID-19 were fever, and acute respiratory problems. These situations lead to the admission of the patients in the hospitals in the Multan.

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